

PSYCHOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article is based on the psychological principles of foreign language teaching. And containing the theories of scientists. The article explains that the psychological approach is more effective when teaching language to children. Opinions have been expressed on the theories of Clyne and Nariswariatmojo. The article explains how teachers should teach children on the basis of psychological principles and how many groups it should be divided into.

Keywords: Developmental, social, . Strategic Thinking, Intrinsic motivation, Assessment, affective, psychological principles, Learning Process.

INTRODUCTION: Learning a dialect may be a complex, time-intensive errand that requires commitment, tirelessness, and difficult work. In the event that you're perusing this, at that point you likely as of now know that. What you might not know is that there are procedures that can assist you think about more viably, so that you just make the foremost of your time and energy. This present to begin with clarifies a few of the key standards that guide viable dialect learning, and after that portrays exercises that can assist you put these standards into hone. Utilize these apparatuses to form a key consider arrange that makes a difference your dialect abilities grow. Key principles of language learning The Basics: First, let's conversation almost the nuts and bolts. Investigate in this range (called "second dialect acquisition" in the scholarly community) recommends that there are three key components to learning a unused language. The to begin with is comprehensible input, which could be a favor way of saying being uncovered to (hearing or perusing) something within the modern dialect and learning to get it it. Comprehensible output is the moment component, and obviously it implies learning to create (talk or compose) something within the unused language. The third component is review or feedback, which essentially implies distinguishing mistakes and making changes in response.

Methods: Concurring to Clyne, 'there are colossal cognitive contrasts between youthful grown-ups and creating children. Clyne advance expressed that language specialists and teachers 'subscribe to the see that's a organic timetable for ideal dialect learning which stymies the endeavors of youths and youthful grown-ups

to secure the language.' Frankfurt Universal School (2016) concurred and expressed 'Children, who as of now have strong education abilities in their claim dialect, seem to be within the best position to procure a modern dialect productively while while 'motivated, more seasoned learners can be very fruitful as well, they as a rule battle to attain native-speaker-equivalent articulation and intonation.' Clyne expressed that other scholar connected this line of thinking 'due to the truth of the distinctive brain versatility at distinctive ages and others accept that the more seasoned learner will get a handle on the dialect speedier as they can accomplish an expository understanding of the unused dialect though, children can as it were get it in concrete terms.' In a contrary view that adolescents learn another language quicker, Clyne stated that 'adolescents can add a child-like willingness to experiment and play with language to this capacity for metalinguistic awareness so they become quick learners.' Based on her evaluation of the different views, Clyne stated that generally, studies reveal that cognitive factors such as verbal intelligence, phonological processing ability and long term memory capacity strongly influence the student's ability to learn a second language. Nariswariatmojo expressed that 'if the lesson doesn't curiously to the understudy, the understudy can't learn well.' In the event that understudies are constrained to do the dialect at that point it implies students' are not intrigued and so they would put less exertion in something they are not fascinated by. I see the control of intrigued in my classroom day by day. I endeavor to get a handle on my student's intrigued by letting them know how certain scientific concepts are utilized within the genuine world and how it can offer assistance them some time recently I can instruct it. My understudy Justinus Justin has this address he likes to inquire once I don't say where it utilized, 'Miss what we ought to learn that for?' Once, I donate an clarification, I can see him work with more dedication and vigor. Something else, he would say, 'I will fair skip that on the test.' Intrigued guarantees attention. Attention is an critical viewpoint of learning. On the off chance that we don't have understudies consideration, they will not be learning as they will not be centered sufficient to get a handle on the concept. In dialect learners, consideration is basic particularly since the English-language has numerous rules and exemptions.

The LCP were put together by the American Psychological Association. The following 14 psychological principles pertain to the learner and the learning process.

The 14 principles are divided into those referring to:

- Cognitive and metacognitive
- Motivational and affective

- Developmental and social
- Individual difference factors

COGNITIVE AND METACOGNITIVE FACTOR

1. Nature of Learning Process
2. Goals of the Learning Process
3. Construction of Knowledge
4. Strategic Thinking
5. Thinking about thinking
6. Context of Learning

MOTIVATIONAL AND AFFECTIVE FACTOR

7. Motivational and emotional influences on learning
8. Intrinsic motivation to learn
9. Effects of motivation on effort

DEVELOPMENTAL AND SOCIAL FACTOR

10. Developmental influences on learning
11. Social influences on learning

INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES FACTOR

12. Individual differences in learning
13. Learning and diversity
14. Standards and assessment

Alexander and Murphy gave a summary of the 14 principles and distilled them into five areas:

1. The knowledge base

One's knowledge serves as the foundation of all future learning.

2. Strategic processing and control

Learners can develop skills to reflect and regulate their thoughts and behaviors in order to learn more effectively.

3. Motivation and affect

Factors such as intrinsic motivation, reasons for wanting to learn, personal goals and enjoyment of learning tasks all have a crucial role in the learning process.

4. Development and Individual Differences

Learning is a unique journey for each person because each learner has his own unique combination of genetic and environmental factors that influence him.

5. Situation or context

Learning happens in the context of a society as well as within an individual.

I have learned in this topic the 14 important learner-centered principle that we can use or apply when we are teaching. I have realized that every topic in this subject is very important, so that we need to study hard for it for us to make our

job in the future not so hard. As a future educator I need to apply this 14 learner-centered principle to make my teaching strategy effective and my students will learn many things from me.

CONCLUSION: The process of preparing this course work I have gained and learned a variety of information. I learned that a psychological approach and teaching based on children's behavior is very important in teaching English. I have studied the opinions of many scholars about this. And I have the information I will need in the future. Teaching children in a way that suits their character has a positive effect on them during the lesson. And I got to know a lot of facts. one fact for example: when a child is taught aloud rather than taught in a low voice, the child's memory stays better. And from my own experience and observation, I want to say that children have different behaviors and levels of knowledge as well as levels of interest.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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